

The mechanical response of braided composite tube under three points bending loading

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ABSTRACT

In this study, the mechanical response of braided composite tube under three points bending loading was studied by experimental and numerical method. Various reinforcements with different bundle orientation indicated by braiding angle were fabricated using over-braiding technology and then cured into composite tubes in a VARTM process. A series of three-point bending tests were performed to examine the damage process and extent from initiation to complete failure. Two distinct failure modes in terms of top surface failure characterized by the debonding between matrix and fabric and rear surface failure characterized by penetrating crack of resin were observed, which consequently leads to different mechanical response. The experimental data indicated that the higher strength can be achieved by increasing the braiding angle, which also increases the tendency to the bottom surface failure.

1 INTRODUCTION

As one of textile manufacturing methods, the circular braiding process can be combined with resin transfer molding infusion technology, yielding a considerable potential for cost-efficient production of composite structure^[1]. In comparison to other textile forming methods, such as weaving and knitting, the over-braiding process, forming a seamless multi-layers fabric over a shaped mandrel, enables production of near net-shaped preforms for hollow structures^[2].

Hollow composite part is one of common engineering structures, which can be used to build frame for preventing the loading. There have been a number of literatures concerning the collapse response and energy absorption capacity of braided composite structure. Chui investigated on the effect of braiding angle and yarn content on crush failure characteristics under the axial compression loading^[3,4]. Zhang studied the failure mechanisms and energy absorption characteristic of multi-layer 2D tri-axially braided composite tubes made of glass fiber^[5].

With the development of Finite element method, numerical model was employed to simulate the bending process of braided composite tube and attempt to address failure mechanisms under quasi-static compression. Bear developed a numerical model for representative volume of braided composite tube to calculate its effective stiffness^[6]. Zhang presented a user defined material model which incorporate fiber and matrix damage properties obtained the mechanical response of REV(Representative elementary volume) and then applied it a homogenous model^[7]. Xiao simulated the crush process of braided composite tube by employing a damage constitutive model in LS-DYNA software^[8]. Miravete developed an analytical meso mechanical approach for a unit cell in 3D braided composite materials, which considered the geometry and the mechanical properties of both fiber and matrix^[9]. Huang investigated a progressive crushing process of composite tubes with triggers by numerical method^[10]. McGregor established a continuum damage mechanics to capture the complete tensile and compressive response of braided composite part^[11].

In many industry application, the loading also comes from the lateral direction. Therefore, the transverse crashworthiness signifies a key issue for the lightweight design of vehicle body structures in crash scenarios. However, there have also been a few papers that concerned on the transverse collapse

of composite tube. Mamalis et. al analyzed the crashworthy behaviors of cantilever, thin-wall glass fiber reinforced plastic tubes with square and rectangular cross-section in bending. Strum performed a quasi-static four-point-bending tests to verify the role of hybridization of the braiding yarn on the energy absorption capacity of C-shaped braided composite frame^[12]. The experimental data showed that the fracture behavior of braided composites can be influenced significantly by the modification of the fiber architecture in the web. Zhou, H., et al., conducted a finite element analyses on transverse impact behaviors of 3-D circular composite tubes with different braiding angles^[13]. The difference of intra-layer of braided reinforcement didn't mentioned in these literatures. The over-braiding manufacturing technology offers the possibility to influence the fracture mechanics by adjustment of the bundle orientation. Therefore, the transverse mechanical responses of braided composite tube with difference of bundle orientation have not been reported comprehensively so far.

This study is thus conducted to determine the bending stiffness and energy absorption capacity of the braided composite tube and demonstrate that the mechanical response of composite tube is dependent of bundle orientation. To fulfill this objective, a series of three-point bending tests have been performed to examine the damage process and extent from imitation to complete breakage. The preparation of the braided composite tubes, the experiment test-bench and the associated instrumentation used in this study are described. And the experimental results are analyzed in detail.

2 QUASI-STATIC THREE-POINT BENDING TESTS

Three-point tests were conducted to determine flexural performance of the composite tube, which were performed in a universal testing machine. Two rollers were used to support the test specimen. A cross-head with a constant moving velocity pressed the specimen downward. The span length, total length and width were 100, 130 and 10mm, respectively. The wall thickness of the specimen was 2mm. All of the tests were carried out at constant crosshead velocity of 2mm/min. A camera was used to record the photography of tested specimen. And the bending deflection at the bottom surface of tube was measured using a dial indicator which mounted under the specimen.

3 SPECIMEN PREPARATION

The braided fabric was interlaced onto a cylinder mandrel with 20mm diameter using a circular braiding machine with 24 carriers, which was subsequently cured into composite tube. Toray T700SC-12K carbon fibers were used as braiding bundle. Vinyl ester resin (Type RF-1001, Shanghai Sino Composite Co., Ltd, China), was infused into the fabric with a resin transfer molding technology to produce the braided composite tube. After being cured at room temperature (20°C) for 12 hours, the composite tube was extracted from the mandrel and cut into 130mm-long specimens. The braided fabric was interlaced onto a mandrel by a circular braiding machine. The various braided structures whose braiding angles are 40, 45, 50 and 60 degree respectively, were got by adjusting the translation speed of the mandrel. A numerical model at tow-scale consisting of braided fabric and resin was established to analyze the bending response. The geometric model of single tow is obtained by sweeping the section along a certain braiding trajectory. The element type of C3D8R was chosen to model them, while four-node solid element (C3D4) was used to mesh the resin. The tow and resin were meshed together to make sure they shared the same nodes on the interface for guaranteeing the computational accuracy.

4 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1 summary of experimental data

The experimental data results show that the braiding structure has a significant influence on the bending stiffness and specific energy absorption. Figure 1 plotted the curve of pressure head displacement versus resistance force. The similar trend is found in all specimens except for the one marked as 60_1. And all experimental data were listed in Table.1 As the pressure head moved downward, the composite tube generated the resistance force to balance the head. After the peak force

is achieved, the resistance force progressively decreased while the damage developed gradually. The peak force of composite tube was also found to increase with the braiding angle, which means a larger fiber volume fraction.

Table.1: The experimental data in the tests

No.	Failure mode	P_max (kN)	P_mean (kN)	Total energy (J)	SEA(j/g)
[±40]S-1	Top failure	0.9308	0.6022	15.056	0.7511
[±40]S-2	Top failure	0.9329	0.6385	15.9617	0.7963
[±40]S-3	Top failure	0.9385	0.5959	14.8968	0.7431
Average Value		0.9341	0.6122	15.3048	0.7635
[±50]S-1	Top failure	1.2281	0.9495	23.7368	1.1630
[±50]S-2	Top failure	1.1155	0.9121	22.8034	1.1173
[±50]S-3	Top failure	1.1577	0.7742	19.3561	0.9484
Average Value		1.1671	0.8786	21.9654	1.0762
[±60]S-1	Bottom failure	1.2561	0.7033	17.5816	0.8562
[±60]S-2	Top failure	1.3054	1.049	26.2239	1.2770
[±60]S-3	Top failure	1.2482	0.9885	24.7116	1.2034
Average Value		1.2699	0.9136	22.8390	1.1122

Figure 1 Displacement–force curve of braided composite tube with different fabric structure

4.2 deformation of cross-section

The numerical model revealed the deformation of composite tube during bending in a clear manner. The cross-section deformation of composite tube was illustrated in Figure 2. On the top surface, the tube was flattened under the impact of pressure head. Because the maximum displacement occurred at the head position, the peeling of resin was observed. Although the carbon tow was separated from the resin in the middle, it also provided considerable resistance due to the intact combination on the two sides. The peeling area increased as the pressure head continued to move down. There were obvious differences in varying structure of reinforcement. Figure 3 showed the top surface pictures of composite tube. The peeling area was largest in the composite tube with 40o braiding angle and the smallest area was found in the composite tube with 60o braiding angle. It was attributed to the high fiber volume fraction coming up with large braiding angle.

Figure 2: The deformation of cross-section of tube at $z = 0$

Figure 3: The peeling area of braided composite tube with different fabric structure

Figure 4: the photograph of broken composite tube with 60° braiding angle

4.3 the two failure modes

There was a sharp decline in the displacement–force curve for the specimen 60_1. And the photograph of specimen 60_1 from side view was depicted in the Figure 4. A penetrating crack of resin occurred in the bottom and flange surface. For clearer clarifying the generation and development of the crack, some key frames marked as A, B and C, respectively were captured on the displacement–force curve. It can be drawn that the bending stiffness decreases abruptly as the crack spacing increasing.

Figure 5: breakage occurring on the bottom surface of composite tube with large braiding angle

9 CONCLUSIONS

The bending failure of braided composite tubes with different bundle orientation and stacking sequence was investigated under three-point loading. During the test, the specimen presents the deformation in cross-section and bending deformation. The difference between the displacement of indenter roller and dial indicator was used to measure the deformation of cross-section. The differences of transverse energy absorption of composite tube with different bundle orientation and stacking sequence were investigated. Two failure modes were observed. In top surface failure mode, the crack occurs in the contact point of the indenter roller. The cross-section of composite tube deforms in top surface and consequently the resin is progressively peeled from the braided fabric, which decreases the stiffness of composite tube gradually. In bottom surface failure mode, resin tensile failure near the mid-span causing the load to sharp drop to zero. In general, three specimens were tested separately for each configuration to validate and to average the two tests responses. The specimens present a pronounced linear behavior with a very distinct drop after cracking occurs. The top surface failure mode has higher SEA value than the bottom surface failure mode.

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